

**THE ROLE OF RADIOLOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC METHODS IN THE
DIFFERENTIAL DIANOSIS OF THYROID NODULES AND MALIGNANT
TUMORS IN THYROID DISEASES.**

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Annotation: *Thyroid nodules are a common finding in clinical practice. Approximately 5–15% of thyroid nodules are malignant and the incidence of thyroid cancer is increasing due to various factors. Various imaging techniques and procedures have been developed for the differential diagnosis of thyroid nodules. These imaging techniques include ultrasonography (US), computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).*

Keywords : *Thyroid nodule, Thyroid cancer, Ultrasonography, Computed tomography, Magnetic resonance imaging.*

Qalqonsimo bez kasalliklarida tugunlar va yomon sifatli o‘smalarini differensial diagnostika qilishda nur tashxis usullarining ahamiyati

Annotatsiya: *Qalqonsimon bez tugunlari klinik amaliyotda keng tarqalgandir. Qalqonsimon bez tugunlarining taxminan 5-15% i yomon sifatli va turli omillar tufayli qalqonsimon bezning saraton kasalligi ortib bormoqda. Qalqonsimon bez tugunlarining differensial diagnostikasi uchun turli xil tasvirlash usullari va protseduralari ishlab chiqilgan. Ushbu tasvirlash usullariga ultratovush (UT), kompyuter tomografiyasi (KT) va magnit-rezonans tomografiya (MRI) kiradi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Qalqonsimon bez tugunlari, Qalqonsimon bez saratoni, Ultrasonografiya, Kompyuter tomografiya, Magnit-rezonans tomografiya*

Роль методов лучевой диагностики в дифференциальной диагностике узлов и злокачественных опухолей при заболеваниях щитовидной железы.

Аннотация: *Узлы щитовидной железы являются распространенной находкой в клинической практике. Примерно 5–15% узлов щитовидной железы являются злокачественными и заболеваемость раком щитовидной железы увеличивается из-за различных факторов. Для дифференциальной диагностики узлов щитовидной железы были разработаны различные методы и процедуры*

визуализации. Эти методы визуализации включают ультразвуковое исследование (УЗИ), компьютерную томографию (КТ) и магнитно-резонансную томографию (МРТ).

Ключевые слова: Узел щитовидной железы, Рак щитовидной железы, Ультрасонография, Компьютерная томография, Магнитно-резонансная томография.

Introduction. Thyroid nodules are discrete lesions in the thyroid gland that are distinct from the surrounding parenchyma. Recently, the incidence of thyroid nodule has been increasing year by year, making it one of the most common diseases of the thyroid system, with occult thyroid nodule accounting for 65% of the total population . According to the report, approximately 5% of thyroid nodules are at risk of developing thyroid cancer, with thyroid carcinoma becoming the most common tumour in the head and neck region [8]. Thyroid cancer is a common malignant disease that accounts for about 1% of all cancer patients. Solid thyroid nodules are risk factors for thyroid cancer, and it is important to accurately distinguish thyroid nodules. Ultrasonography is the first choice of clinical diagnosis and differentiation of thyroid cancer. However, it is difficult to accurately identify the nodule by the atypical ultrasonic wave characteristics because of the complexity and overlapping property of the thyroid nodule ultrasonic image[3]. In recent years, the incidence rate of thyroid cancer is on the rise. With the wide application of ultrasound technology, ultrasound has become one of the most important means of thyroid detection. Fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNA) is the best non-surgical diagnostic method for thyroid malignant tumor at present, but it is an invasive examination. Improving the accuracy of non-invasive ultrasound diagnosis is helpful to reduce the number of FNA, which is of clinical significance. Although ultrasound has made significant progress in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant thyroid nodules, at present, conventional ultrasound (CUS) combined with color Doppler flow imaging (CDFI) still has a certain rate of missed diagnosis and misdiagnosis in determining the nature of thyroid nodules, and the diagnostic accuracy is not high, and there are also technical limitations in detecting small blood vessels and low blood flow. As a new vascular imaging technology, Superb microvascular imaging (SMI) can visualize low-velocity blood flow. Compared with CDFI, it can describe blood flow in more detail, and can obtain high-quality microvascular images without relying on contrast media, it can also describe the blood flow around the sinus and in the nodule in more detail[2]. Along with the developments in sonoelastography and 3D sonographic techniques, several different quantitative measurement parameters have been used in daily practice. The detection of elasticity index by elastography has been proposed as a supplementary tool in the assessment of thyroid nodules. On the other hand, the use of 3D US and 3D PDUS apart from obstetric radiology has become

increasingly widespread in recent years. Three-dimensional US, 3D PDUS, and computer-aided color Doppler software methods provide a number of advantages over conventional techniques. Three-dimensional US is more accurate than two-dimensional examination in the evaluation of anatomical structures and assessment of disease and provides data that can be subjected to repeated evaluation. Three-dimensional power Doppler US is able to quantify vascularity within organs, tissues and, tumors[1].

Ultrasonography. The management of thyroid nodules is controversial because of the high detection rate of thyroid nodules and the increasing incidence of thyroid cancer. Although the prevalence of palpable thyroid nodules is low (3%–4%), incidental thyroid nodules are detected at a rate of 17%–67% with ultrasonography (US), 16%–17% with neck computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans, 1%–2% with 18F-fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG)-positron emission tomography (PET)/CT scans and 60% in autopsy specimens. Thyroid malignancy was detected in 5% of patients with palpable thyroid nodules, in 8%–12% of non-palpable nodules evaluated using fine-needle aspiration (FNA) and in 36% of the evaluated autopsy specimens. Although the incidence of all sizes and stages of thyroid cancer, as well as thyroid cancer-related mortality, has increased, early detection of low-risk small papillary thyroid carcinomas (PTCs) by US has contributed to the increased incidence of thyroid cancer over the last 20 years. Increased detection of low-risk small PTC is associated with overdiagnosis and overtreatment. Therefore, the risk profiles of patients and thyroid nodules should be taken into consideration in the diagnosis and management of thyroid cancer[4]. So, US is a sensitive method for the detection and diagnosis of thyroid nodules. There is no risk of radiation exposure, and it can evaluate changes in the thyroid parenchyma and examine LNs. Although the combination of US features can help differentiate benign from malignant thyroid nodules, some features of benign and malignant nodules overlap. This may lead to unnecessary biopsy of benign nodules, which can increase medical expenditures and complications[7]. US-based risk stratification systems (RSSs) or Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) can be used to assess the malignancy risk in nodules, identify poor prognostic factors in cancer, select patients for biopsy, and determine the optimal management plan for patients with thyroid nodules[4].

Scanning technique. To optimize thyroid US examinations, patients should lie in the supine position with the neck hyperextended. During thyroid US examination, an appropriate scan range is important for comprehensive evaluation of the entire thyroid gland and cervical lymph nodes. The locations of pathologic cervical lymph nodes should be recorded as levels according to the imaging-based nodal classification system. Central neck lymph nodes can be classified as pretracheal, paratracheal, and

prelaryngeal. Scanning of the thyroid gland and central neck should include the transverse plane, through which the transducer sweeps from the submental region to the sternal notch. Transverse scanning of the midline central neck includes the pyramidal lobe, isthmus, and prelaryngeal/pretracheal central neck lymph nodes (levels 1A and 6); this method can also be used to detect ectopic (accessory) thyroid tissue, thyroglossal duct cysts, and nodules arising from ectopic thyroid tissue. Transverse scanning of the paramedian central neck should include the bilateral thyroid lobes (upper, middle, and lower portions), bilateral paratracheal lymph nodes, and parathyroid lesions in the central neck[6].

CT and MRT. There is insufficient evidence supporting the ability of CT and MRI to differentiate thyroid cancers from benign nodules unless there is evidence of either local tumor invasion or metastasis; however, these methods may be helpful for determining the extent of goiter with intrathoracic or retropharyngeal extension. They may be used as additional modalities if there is a suspicion of advanced thyroid cancer (aerodigestive tract or recurrent laryngeal nerve invasion, lymph node [LN] metastasis). In patients with advanced disease, IV contrast agents should be administered to optimize imaging. CT can define the degree of tracheal compression more effectively than US. Although MRI is an alternative to CT, CT is preferred because it is associated with a lower risk of respiratory motion artifacts, shorter scan time, and a higher resolution. Therefore, CT is more effective for evaluating LNs in the entire neck. However, the preferred modality for a suspected thyroid nodule is US.

The use of CT as an initial imaging test for the diagnosis of thyroid nodules is associated with a relatively high risk of radiation exposure. MRI does not have a risk of radiation exposure; however, MRI requires a longer scan time than US and CT, and it is associated with high medical costs. CT and MRI are not effective for differentiating between benign and malignant thyroid nodules. Given that CT and MRI do not have the spatial resolution to identify suspicious features on US, they should not be used as the primary imaging modality in patients with suspicious thyroid nodules[7].

Elastography. US elastography is a technique that measures tissue elasticity. Cancer tissue is usually harder and firmer than normal thyroid parenchyma or benign nodules. Two representative elastography techniques are used to quantify tissue strain. "Strain elastography" evaluates the degree of tissue deformation induced by compression or acoustic forces. "Shear wave" speed measurement, measures the speed of shear waves that propagate orthogonally to the direction of tissue displacement. The propagation speed is generally higher in malignant thyroid nodules than in benign nodules. Early clinical studies reported that US elastography had a similar or better performance than gray-scale US. However, recent studies have reported that elastography is not superior to gray-scale US for use alone or as a complementary

imaging modality for the diagnosis of thyroid malignancy. Several studies have reported a potential diagnostic role for US elastography in the diagnosis of thyroid nodules with indeterminate or non-diagnostic cytology or indeterminate US features. Further studies are required to establish the complementary role of US elastography in the risk stratification of thyroid nodules[4].

Discussion. Ultrasound plays a critical role in evaluating thyroid nodules. We compared the performance of the two most popular ultrasound malignancy risk stratification systems, the 2015 American Thyroid Association (ATA) guidelines and the American College of Radiology Thyroid Imaging and Reporting Data System (ACR TI-RADS). We retrospectively identified 250 thyroid nodules that were surgically removed from 137 patients. Their ultrasound images were independently rated using both ATA and ACR TI-RADS by six raters with expertise in ultrasound interpretation. For each system, we generated a receiver operating characteristic curve and calculated the area under the curve (AUC). Sixty-five (26%) nodules were malignant. There was “fair agreement” among raters for both ATA and ACR TI-RADS. Our observed malignancy risks for ATA and ACR TI-RADS categories were similar to expected risk thresholds with a few notable exceptions including the intermediate ATA risk category and the three highest risk categories for ACR TI-RADS. Biopsy of 226 of the 250 nodules would be indicated by ATA guidelines based on nodule size and mean ATA rating. One hundred forty-six nodules would be biopsied based on ACR TI-RADS. The sensitivity, specificity, and negative and positive predictive values were 92%, 10%, 79%, and 27%, respectively, for ATA and 74%, 47%, 84%, and 33%, respectively, for ACR TI-RADS. The AUC for ATA was 0.734 and for ACR TI-RADS was 0.718. Although both systems demonstrated good diagnostic performance, ATA guidelines resulted in a greater number of thyroid biopsies and exhibited more consistent malignancy risk prediction for higher risk categories[5].

Conclusion. The conclusion of thyroid US reports the summary findings on general thyroid feature, thyroid nodule, cervical lymph node, extrathyroidal lesion, and biopsy procedure. The conclusion section should also briefly summarize regarding the absence or presence of diffuse thyroid disease; K-TIRADS category, location, and size of significant thyroid nodules; absence or presence of suspicious or enlarged indeterminate lymph nodes; and extrathyroidal lesions (if present). If biopsy was performed for the thyroid nodule or cervical lymph node, a brief description of the procedure and complications (if any) should be reported. Although, In the handful of studies to date that have compared different thyroid nodule ultrasound risk stratification systems, it remains unclear that any single system outperforms the other with respect to statistical or clinical significance. However, these studies have shown

that most of these systems have demonstrated relatively accurate predictions of malignancy, with high sensitivity and NPV. Unfortunately, having so many different rating systems in use can be confusing for both patients and providers. It can also hinder the aggregation and comparison of data in research on thyroid nodules. Moving forward, continuing to work across disciplines and internationally to build consensus guidelines for risk stratification of thyroid nodules is critical because it would provide a common lexicon and framework for multicenter, prospective trials that would benefit patient care and facilitate training of physicians who clinically interpret thyroid ultrasound.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. Cansu A, Ayan E, Kul S, Eyüboğlu İ, Oğuz Ş, Mungan S. Diagnostic value of 3D power Doppler ultrasound in the characterization of thyroid nodules. *Turk J Med Sci.* 2019 Jun 18;49(3):723-729. doi: 10.3906/sag-1803-92. PMID: 31203590; PMCID: PMC7018289.
2. Jiang L, Zhang D, Chen YN, Yu XJ, Pan MF, Lian L. The value of conventional ultrasound combined with superb microvascular imaging and color Doppler flow imaging in the diagnosis of thyroid malignant nodules: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2023 Jun 21;14:1182259. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2023.1182259. PMID: 37415660; PMCID: PMC10321595.
3. Jin H, Wang C, Jin X. Superb microvascular imaging for distinguishing thyroid nodules: A meta-analysis (PRISMA). *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2022 Jun 17;101(24):e29505. doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000029505. PMID: 35713460; PMCID: PMC9276439.
4. Ha EJ, Chung SR, Na DG, Ahn HS, Chung J, Lee JY, Park JS, Yoo RE, Baek JH, Baek SM, Cho SW, Choi YJ, Hahn SY, Jung SL, Kim JH, Kim SK, Kim SJ, Lee CY, Lee HK, Lee JH, Lee YH, Lim HK, Shin JH, Sim JS, Sung JY, Yoon JH, Choi M. 2021 Korean Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System and Imaging-Based Management of Thyroid Nodules: Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology Consensus Statement and Recommendations. *Korean J Radiol.* 2021 Dec;22(12):2094-2123. doi: 10.3348/kjr.2021.0713. Epub 2021 Oct 26. PMID: 34719893; PMCID: PMC8628155.
5. Huang BL, Ebner SA, Makkar JS, Bentley-Hibbert S, McConnell RJ, Lee JA, Hecht EM, Kuo JH. A Multidisciplinary Head-to-Head Comparison of American College of Radiology Thyroid Imaging and Reporting Data System and American Thyroid Association Ultrasound Risk Stratification Systems. *Oncologist.* 2020 May;25(5):398-403. doi: 10.1634/theoncologist.2019-0362. Epub 2019 Nov 19. PMID: 31740569; PMCID: PMC7216459.

6. Lee MK, Na DG, Joo L, Lee JY, Ha EJ, Kim JH, Jung SL, Baek JH. Standardized Imaging and Reporting for Thyroid Ultrasound: Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology Consensus Statement and Recommendation. *Korean J Radiol.* 2023 Jan;24(1):22-30. doi: 10.3348/kjr.2022.0894. PMID: 36606617; PMCID: PMC9830140.
7. Lee JY, Baek JH, Ha EJ, Sung JY, Shin JH, Kim JH, Lee MK, Jung SL, Lee YH, Ahn HS, Yoon JH, Choi YJ, Park JS, Lee YJ, Choi M, Na DG; Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology (KSThR) and Korean Society of Radiology. 2020 Imaging Guidelines for Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer: Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology. *Korean J Radiol.* 2021 May;22(5):840-860. doi: 10.3348/kjr.2020.0578. Epub 2021 Feb 9. PMID: 33660459; PMCID: PMC8076832.
8. Luo H, Yin L. Diagnostic value of superb microvascular imaging and color doppler for thyroid nodules: A meta-analysis. *Front Oncol.* 2023 Apr 5;13:1029936. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2023.1029936. PMID: 37091165; PMCID: PMC10113672.